

Supplementary figures to paper

Rapid Evolution of Host Repertoire and Geographic Range in a Young and Diverse Genus of Montane Butterflies

Figure S1. Altitudinal range for *Colias* species included in the study, colored by biogeographical distribution.

Figure S2. Species Tree inferred by ASTRAL from gene trees of 32 nuclear gene loci containing all samples. The smaller figure in the upper left corner shows the branch lengths. The three values before each node indicate posterior probabilities: local quartet topology (LPP) / gene concordance factor/sequence concordance factor.

Figure S3. nuDNA gene tree inferred with IQ-TREE from 150 nuclear gene loci. The smaller figure in the upper left corner shows the branch lengths. The three support values before each node from IQ-TREE2: Ultrafast bootstrap values/ SH-like approximate likelihood ratio test/ Maximum likelihood bootstrap values.

Figure S4. mtDNA gene tree inferred with IQ-TREE from mitochondrial genomes. The smaller figure in the upper left corner shows the branch lengths. The three support values before each node from IQ-TREE2: Ultrafast bootstrap values/ SH-like approximate likelihood ratio test/ Maximum likelihood bootstrap values.

Figure S5. Species tree constructed with ASTRAL based on 15 mitochondrial gene loci data. LPP values are shown on the branch of each node.

Figure S6. Time-calibrated tree obtained from the MCMCTREE analysis. Node ages are the median of node age posterior distributions. The 95% confidence interval is shown in parentheses.

Figure S7. Joint posterior probability for each pair of categorical (y-axis) and quantitative (x-axis) of regional feature. Left panels show the effect of area and distance while right panels show the effect of altitude on (from top to bottom): between-region speciation, dispersal, extinction, and within-region speciation.

Figure S8. Posterior distribution of speciation rates for geographical ranges of different sizes. Speciation rate increases as range size increases.

Figure S9. Posterior distribution of extinction rates for ranges of different sizes. Extinction rate is similar for ranges with only one area and is zero for larger ranges.

Figure S10. Results of diversification analyses for the second-best model of shifts in diversification within *Colias*.

Figure S11. a) Extant network of interactions between *Colias* species and their host plant genera. Rows and columns are ordered to facilitate the visualization of network modules. Interactions are colored by module and interactions between different modules are in grey. Inferred ancestral networks at b) 1, c) 2, and d) 3 Ma. In b-d, the fewer grey cells, the more robust the modules are.